

Fixation of cesium on titania based ceramic precursor

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Synroc is a titanate ceramic wasteform which comprises essentially rutile TiO_2 , hollandite $\text{Ba}(\text{Al}_2\text{Ti}_6)\text{O}_{16}$, zirconolite $\text{CaZrTi}_2\text{O}_7$ and perovskite CaTiO_3 . These phases have capacity to immobilise all the elements present in high level waste as solid solutions. The phase characterisation and microstructure of the wasteform along with crystallochemical interactions between cesium and the titania based ceramic precursor have been studied. The ceramic precursor has been prepared by oxide route method and the microstructure studied by X-ray powder diffraction. Cesium fixation study (by leach rate for 90 days) shows that it can be fixed in the hollandite phase of the ceramic matrix.

Vitrification of high level liquid nuclear waste using silicate glasses has been a proven and industrially established method for immobilisation of hazardous isotopes^{1,2}. This technology basically involves heating the waste at a higher temperature (1100–1200°). The melting technology suffers from some problems². Alternatively, efforts have been directed to develop multibarrier waste forms of high chemical durability and improved mechanical strength. Ringwood³ reported that the titania based ceramic material can fix ~20 wt% high level waste in its matrix. Such waste forms have excellent integrity and are leach resistant under different geochemical conditions. They can also withstand the hydrothermal conditions of the repositories. Since then the titania based ceramic precursors have attracted attention of several workers⁴. A thermodynamically stable ceramic waste form popularly known as SYNROC (synthetic rock) is also under development which is a multi-assembly of polycrystalline and polyphase ceramic material containing four titanate minerals zirconolite, hollandite, perovskite and rutile. It has been reported that such ceramic precursor incorporate into its crystal nearly all elements present in high level waste as solid solutions^{5,6}. A hot pressed SYNROC is reported to have very low leachability and high mechanical strength. Radioactive cesium and strontium are two isotopes which occur along with actinides and transition metals in the high level waste. Due to very high solubility in water, cesium-137 and strontium-90 are the most difficult isotopes to be immobilised, solidified and fixed in the wastefoms which could withstand the geological and hydrothermal environment for over 10^3 – 10^5 years. It is, therefore, necessary to study the phase characterisation and microstructure of the wastefoms along with crystallochemical interactions between cesium and the titania based ceramic precursor⁷.

Results and Discussion

The powder X-ray diffraction pattern (Fig. 1) of the

ceramic precursor shows the presence of three phases : hollandite ($\text{BaAl}_2\text{Ti}_6\text{O}_{16}$), perovskite (CaTiO_3) and zirconolite ($\text{CaZrTi}_2\text{O}_7$). Their characteristic peak maxima $d = 0.3126$, 0.2811 , 0.2684 nm, respectively, for hollandite, perovskite and zirconolite have been found to match in their position and intensity⁶. Additional peaks due to Ti_3O_7 and rutile have been identified at $d = 0.3477$ and 0.3217 nm, respectively. The X-ray data for hollandite shows 11 reflections between 0.4408 and 0.1191 nm. On the basis of the observed peaks of hollandite, the indexing of the lines on a powder pattern has been attempted following the procedure laid down for tetragonal system where the relationship, $\sin^2 \theta_{hkl} = A(h^2 + k^2) + C l^2$ gives an indication of symmetry⁸. The calculated values of the $\sin^2 \theta$ matches fairly well with the reported ones. The cell parameters⁹ are obtained as $a = b = 5.35$ and $c = 6.25$ Å. Table 1 lists the indexing pattern of 11 lines of hollandite.

Fig. 1. X-Ray powder diffraction pattern of the ceramic precursor.

Table 1. X-Ray powder diffraction pattern of synthetic hollandite phase of ceramic precursor

<i>d</i> (Å)	θ	$\sin^2\theta_{\text{obs}}$	$\sin^2\theta_{\text{cal}}$	<i>hkl</i>
3.77	11.7650	0.04157	0.04131	110
3.12	14.2625	0.06069	0.06064	002
2.47	18.1675	0.09720	0.09777	201
2.29	19.6550	0.11313	0.10320	210
2.21	20.3225	0.12062	0.11885	211
2.04	22.1500	0.14215	0.14302	202
1.98	22.8300	0.15054	0.15700	103
1.80	25.1900	0.18115	0.18039	221
1.69	27.0875	0.20734	0.20655	310
1.55	29.7275	0.24589	0.24649	302
1.40	33.2150	0.30006	0.30159	223

Pseudotetragonal

$A = 0.020655$, $a = 5.35$, $C = 0.015151$, $c = 6.25$.

Table 2 compares the *d* maxima (nm) of the phases present in titania based precursor.

Table 2. Values of *d* maxima (nm) of the phases in Ti-based precursor

Mineral	Observed maxima	Reported maxima
Hollandite	0.312, 0.347	0.314, 0.311
Zirconolite	0.255, 0.180	0.253, 0.182
Perovskite	0.190, 0.268	0.191, 0.272
Rutile	0.169, 0.247	0.169, 0.249

The ceramic precursor was calcined with cesium chloride at 1150° for 3 h. The cesium loaded ceramic so obtained was subjected to leachability test for cesium. The short term (24 h) leachability test was carried out (in triplicate) on three samples (A, B and C) drawn from three different sites of both the pre-heated and post-heated bulk phase as shown in Table 3. The leach rate data for 90 days are summarised in Table 4. The cesium fixation in the titania based ceramic phase is attributed to the formation of hollandite phase of precursor. The hollandite phase of precursor contains barium, cesium and minor amounts of rubidium as tunnel cations, and aluminium and titanium as trivalent species. The hollandite phase of ceramic precursor has following structural formula $\text{Ba}_x\text{Cs}_y(\text{Ti}, \text{Al})_{2x+y}^{3+}\text{Ti}_{8-2x-y}^{4+}\text{O}_{16}$ ($x = 0.66$). The replacement of barium by cesium results in an increase of tunnel site occupancy and is accompanied by readjustment of superstructure to a configuration of higher multiplicity¹⁰. The plots of cumulative %Cs leached vs leach time (in days) for pre- and post-heated precursor samples show that in preheated sample all the Cs^+ is leached out in first two days and attains the plateau value¹¹, while in post-heated sample the leaching of Cs^+ is constant in first seven days and from 12th. day onwards it increases from 16 to 25.3% in 90 days while 74.7% of cesium still remaining fixed in the ceramic matrix. In powdered sample near surface microvoids provide a large reservoir of cesium

which could be accessed via the rapid diffusion paths furnished by intergranular films¹². Thus, the overall leachability approximately reduces four times in the post-heated sample.

Table 3. Short term leaching data of Cs^+ from ceramic precursor at 25°

Sample	Cs^+ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) in		% Cs fixed in hollandite
	Pre-calcined	Post-calcined	
A	33	1.8	94.54
B	36	2.0	94.44
C	37	2.2	94.05

Table 4. Leaching profile of Cs^+ from the powdered ceramic precursor

Initial Cs^+ present (A_0) = 30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Wt. of precursor = 25 mg, vol. of the leachant = 25 ml.

Leach time	ΣA_n ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Cumulative %Cs released
1	3.0	10.0
2	3.6	12.0
3	3.6	12.0
4	3.6	12.0
5	3.6	12.0
7	3.6	12.0
12	4.8	16.0
15	4.8	16.0
30	7.6	25.3
36	8.2	27.3
40	7.6	25.3
65	7.6	25.3
90	7.6	25.3

Cumulative %Cs released = $\Sigma A_n \times 100/A_0$; A_0 = initial Cs^+ present in sample ($\mu\text{g/ml}$), ΣA_n = sum of Cs^+ present in sample after leaching ($\mu\text{g/ml}$).

Experimental

The ceramic precursor was synthesised by the oxide route method¹³ having the following composition (wt%) : TiO_2 , 36.48; ZrO_2 , 20.79; Al_2O_3 , 24.32; BaO , 9.12; CaO , 9.12. The finely powdered oxide components along with cesium chloride (2 wt% Cs) was homogenised and kept in a furnace at 1150° for 3 h. The ceramic formulation was characterised by densification of the powdered material. The material was rehomogenized using glycerol and its powder diffraction pattern was recorded on a P.W.-1820 diffractometer using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ (1.54 Å) radiation. The leaching study was carried out on a powder sample using the MCC-1 technique¹⁴.

The sample (25 mg) was kept with water (25 ml) and static leaching of cesium content was observed at 25° over a period of 90 days as per time interval mentioned in Table 4. All experiments were performed in triplicate. The

leachant was analysed for cesium by GBC-902 D/B atomic absorption spectrophotometer at wavelength 852.1 nm.

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